

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B046
 Date: 30 Aug 2004
 Take Off: 10:02:17
 Landing: 14:49:44
 Flight Time: 4h47m27

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – flight to investigate radiative impact of aerosols along Adriatic Sea.

Operating Area: N Adriatic, near Venice, N Italy

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Co-pilot 2	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
8	TDL / WAS / PAN / Tubes	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
11	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
12	AMS	Keith Bower	UMIST
13	VACC	Stuart Heath	FAAM
14	Mission Scientist 2	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
15	Mission Scientist 3	Nicolas Bellouin	Met Office
16	Mission Scientist 3	Gunnar Myhre	Oslo University
17	Mission Scientist 4	Jolene Cook	Reading University
18	Nephelometer	Maureen Smith	FAAM
19	Instrument checks	Ken Dewey	FAAM
20	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight

Flight Track:

B046 Track 30-AUG-04

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B046

Date: 30.08.2004

Project: ADRIEX

Location: Italy, Adriatic

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
082200		UBBRs	0.0 kft	024	Covers removed
094805		INU to NAV	0.0 kft	024	
100217		T/O	0.0 kft	249	From Treviso
101004		JW cal complete	5.0 kft	127	
101424	101807	Profile 1	5.0 - 1.9 kft	156	1000ft/min
101807	102049	Profile 1	1.9 - 0.10 kft	156	500ft/min
102058	102232	Profile 2	0.53 - 2.0 kft	166	
102517	103517	Run 1	2.0 kft	345	down sun 2000 ft
103723	104723	Run 2	2.0 kft	171	into sun
104803	104905	Profile 3	2.0 - 1.5 kft	170	500ft/min
105101	110058	Run 3	1.5 kft	351	down sun
110205	110348	Profile 4	1.5 - 1.0 kft	355	
110540	111506	Run 4	1.0 kft	180	into sun
111702	112701	Run 5	1.0 kft	005	down sun
112925	113019	Profile 5	1.0 - 1.5 kft	191	500ft/min
113028	114029	Run 6	1.5 kft	190	into sun
114039	114159	Profile 6	1.5 - 2.0 kft	190	
114407	115407	Run 7	2.0 kft	016	
115535	115714	Profile 7	2.0 - 1.0 kft	280	500ft/min
120234	120401	Orbit 1	1.0 kft	079	bank angle 37 deg
120520	120652	Orbit 2	1.0 kft	043	
120827	121001	Orbit 3	1.0 kft	315	
121040	121312	Orbit 4	1.0 kft	289	
122245	122409	Orbit 5	1.0 kft	307	
122546	122712	Orbit 6	1.0 kft	222	
123052	130221	Run 8	1.0 kft	147	
130232	130623	Profile 9	1.0 - 3.2 kft	144	500ft/min
130634	130920	Profile 9	3.4 - 6.0 kft	145	1000ft/min
131140	133023	Run 9	6.0 - 4.0 kft	326	
133040	133330	Run 10	4.0 - 3.5 kft	323	
133330	133714	Profile 10	3.4 - 0.1 kft	327	
133850	133951	Orbit 7	1.0 kft	100	
134059	134202	Orbit 8	1.0 kft	136	
134254	134357	Orbit 9	1.0 kft	034	
134443	134549	Orbit 10	1.0 kft	317	
134748	135050	Profile 12	1.0 - 4.0 kft	326	N.B.there is no profile 11
135300	141122	Run 11	4.0 kft	326	
141503	141629	Profile 13	0.1 - 1.1 kft	154	500ft/min
141652		Profile 13	1.0 - 15.0 kft	152	1000ft/min
141942		interrupt P13	4.3 kft	152	
142144		restart P13	4.3 kft	317	
142327		interrupt P13	6.0 kft		
142557		restart P13	6.0 kft		
142947		interrupt P13	9.9 kft		
143130		restart P13	10.0 kft		
143703		end P13	15.0 kft	334	
144944		Land	0.0 kft	290	Treviso
145304	final	GPS posn. 45 39.16N 12 12.06E			
145304	final	INU posn. 45 37.58N 12 13.21E			

B046 Track 30-AUG-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight number: B046

Date 30th August 2004

Purpose: ADRIEX flight to investigate radiative impact of aerosols along Adriatic Sea.

Weather: Predominantly cloud free with significant pollution.

Flight pattern

1. Take off Treviso 10:00Z and maneuver at low level to point A (Ocean Tower: 45°18'50''N, 12°30'28''E) (10mins).
2. Stacked profile ascent with ~4 SLRs of ~10minutes durations orientated into- and down- sun at various different levels above, within, and below the aerosol layer (suggest ~100ft – FL80) (60mins).
3. From point A stacked profile descent with ~4 SLRs of ~10minutes durations orientated into- and down- sun at various different levels above, within, and below the aerosol layer (suggest FL90 - 100ft) (110mins).
4. Set of 4 banked orbits at point A banked at solar zenith angle (~40degrees) at 400ft (120mins)
5. Holding pattern of 10 minutes duration (130mins)
6. Set of 4 banked orbits at point A banked at solar zenith angle at 500ft (140mins).
7. SLR oriented down the Adriatic sea heading at 250ft for ~40minutes. (180mins)
8. Profile up to within the aerosol layer. (190mins)
9. SLR within the aerosol layer on reciprocal heading towards point A for ~40minutes (230mins).
10. Broken profile ascent over point A to FL240 (260mins).
11. Broken profile descent over point A to 5000ft (280mins)
12. Recover to Treviso.

(Date printed 30th August 2004)

Good in-situ measurements were made including the PSAP which was recorded off-line on Paola Formenti's laptop. The general situation was that the spatial inhomogeneity of the aerosol and cloud were both high.

Problems:

Ci intrusions.

PSAP recorded onto Paola's laptop.

PCASP missing 3 smallest channels.

Some problems with Horace screens locking (not Horace crashing though).

3000
- 6000ft

Aircraft Scientist's Log

→ 4000 ft
 3.5
 4.5
 15.5
 Page of

Flight No **B.046**.....

Date **30th August 2004**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Delay waiting for high level cloud to dissipate. Moving to the S&E from MSG data.
10:02 Z					T/O - hazy with scattered Cu. More significant st to East. Top of haze @ 4000ft
10:13 Z					More hazy below now. Cb to East, small Cu over land
10:14:24	Sk P1	5000ft ↓	156T		Same Ci ahead to S.
10:18:07		to 500ft/min			2600ft top of aerosol layer
					Very low level aerosol layer - Fog!!! No visibility
	Sk P2				Profile abandoned.
10:25:17	Sk R1	2000ft →			Down-sun run. In top of brown aerosol layer.
10:35:17	End R1	2000ft →			Nephelometer behaving well.
					13.5 abs × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻³
					198.0 nept × 10 ⁻⁶ m ⁻³
10:37:23	Sk R2	2000ft →			No into-sun horizon at all really. Some very patchy Sc below at ~ 1500ft. A few contrails No Ci above, but a # little to the sides.
10:47:23	End R2	2000ft →			

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** 046.....

 Date **30th August 2004**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:48:03	P3 st	2000 -1500ft	170		Short profile neph signal
10:49:05	End P3	1500ft ↓			increases sharply here.
					A few contrails above.
10:51:01	st R3	→ 1500ft			Down-sun run
					No horizon.
					Some contrails above
					Mucky haze - in tops or just above it.
11:00:58	End R3				
11:02:05	st P4	1500ft ↓			Start P4 at 500 ft/minute.
11:03:48	End P4	1000ft.			
11:05:40	st R4	→ 1000ft			<u>Into sun run</u> PCASP
					Free from Ci above.
					Just a few cu at extreme end of run - a little in and out.
11:17:02	st R5	→ 1000ft			<u>Down-sun</u> PCASP heaters ON
					Heavy pollution to the west.
					Lighter to the RHS.
					2000 CUE Very little Ci.
					400 - 450/cc VACC.
					650 PCASP (missing 3 channels)
					Quite heavy pollution at N.
					end of run sca-green = $501 \times 10^{-6} m^{-1}$
11:27:01	End R5	→ 1000ft			Shallow

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Lat \uparrow 44.55
 Lon \downarrow 12.56 Plane 44.86
12.7E

Flight No **B...046**.....

Date **30th August 2004**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:29:25	PS \uparrow	1000 -1500ft	190T		Into-sun profile PCASP heaters ON
11:30:14	End PS				
11:30:28	St \uparrow P6	1500ft	189T		Into-sun PCASP heaters = OFF into sun out 11:33:00
					Very tenuous Ci - nothing to affect radiation measurements.
11:40:29	End \rightarrow R6	1500ft	192T		
11:40:39	St \uparrow P6	1500-2000ft			
11:41:59	End \uparrow P6	2000ft			2000ft Down-sun run
11:50:13	St \uparrow R7				Some Cu to LHS - may affect upper BBRs, but not really... A little Ci above.
11:54:07	End \uparrow R7	2000ft			
11:55:35	St \uparrow P7	2000ft			
11:57:21	End \uparrow P7	1000ft			To much Ci above Pt A to perform orbits.
					Deemed Repositioning.
12:02:34	St \uparrow O1	1000ft			Haywood Monopoles A little Ci above, but not
12:04:00	End \uparrow O1	1000ft			much. Banked at 38° = sea
12:05:20	St \uparrow O2	1000ft			Still a pesky patch of Ci
12:06:52	End \uparrow O2	1000ft			at one point in orbit \rightarrow could be removed if we're clever.
12:08:27	St \uparrow O3	1000ft			300T \rightarrow Ci patch
12:10:03	End \uparrow O3	1000ft			

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B. 046**

 Date **30th August 2004**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Follow
12:11:40	St 04	1000ft			Abit too much Ci for my liking.....
12:13:14	End 04	1000ft			
12:22:45	St 05	1000ft			SZA = 40°
12:24:09	End 05	1000ft			Still too much Ci I think in some of the positions.
12:25:47	St 06	1000ft			"
					Only 2 arbits as Ci interfering. Check upper camera to remove.
12:27:11	End 06	1000ft			
12:30:52	St 7 R07	1000ft			Down Adriatic
12:42:00					Nephelometer scattering dropping to much cleaner levels ~ $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^{-1}$ in plane
13:02:52	End R07 Start Profile 9	1000ft			500 ft/minute through shallow Cu tops at 1900 ft, broad band of Cu below.
13:06:10					Increase to 1000ft/min at 3000ft
13:09:20	End P9	6000ft			Turning onto reciprocal heading above Cu.
13:11:40	St R08 End R	6000ft			Some Ci above.

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4

Aircraft Scientist's Log

44.4N
13.4E

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Date **30th August 2004**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:27:04	St Prof	6000ft ↓			Profile to 4000ft caused by
13:30:40	End P / St R10	4000ft →			ATC. Would rather 6000ft, but vetoed.
13:34:16	End R10 / St P10	4000ft ↓			Ci ahead & above
	End P10	1000ft ↘			Good position for orbits.
	St 07	1000ft ↘			Very little Ci
13:39:51	End 07	1000ft ↘			" 07 Good!
13:40:59	St 08	1000ft ↘			" 08 Good!
13:42:02	End 08	"			" 09 Good!
13:42:44	St 09	"			" 010 Good!
	End 09	"			" Performed under
13:44:44	St 010	"			" the persistent
13:45:49	End 010	"			" plume.
13:47:48	St P12	1000ft ↑			UP from 1000ft at 1000 ft/min.
13:50:50	End P12	4000ft			Cb to LHS over land.
13:53:00	St R11	4000ft			Towards A. \mathcal{R} show well on aircraft radar.
					Just in the top of the
					pollution layer, mostly above
					though.
	End R11	4000ft			Aerosol right down to surface
					except very close to land, where
					might get underneath.
					Dirty descent for positioning,
					can use data 1000ft & lower.
14:15:03	St P14	100 ft ↑		~ Point A.	Profile ascent
					500ft/min → 1000ft

1000ft/min 1000ft↑

Ships about with chemical tracers

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B046

Date: 30/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:14:39	330										Start Profile 1 from 5000'
10:15:33	270										4000'
10:16:35	410										3000'
10:18:00	600										2000'
10:19:46	900										1000'
10:21:02	2000										End of Profile 1, start Profile 2
10:22:32											End of Profile 2 @ 2000'
10:25:18											Start Run 1 @ 2000'
10:26:00	1000										
10:27:00	800										
10:28:00	820										
10:30:00	775										
10:32:00	600										
10:34:00	500										
10:35:20											End of Run 1
10:37:24											Start Run 2 @ 2000'
10:38:00	650										
10:40:00	600										
10:42:00	400										
10:44:00	430										
10:46:00	700										
10:47:26											End of Run 2
10:48:07											Start Profile 3 from 2000'
10:49:05											End of Profile 3 @ 1500'
10:51:01											Start Run 3 @ 1500'
10:52:00	900										
10:54:00	490										
10:56:00	320										
10:57:00	800										
10:58:00	700										
11:00:00	560										
11:01:04											End of Run 3

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 30/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:02:07	600			20							Start profile 4 from 1500'
11:03:50	1200			20							End of Profile 4 @ 1000'
11:05:41											Start Run 4 @ 1000'
11:06:00	1300			20							
11:08:00	650			20							
11:10:00	1000		ON	20							
11:12:00	530		63	10							
11:14:00	500			10							
11:15:09											End of Run 4 PCASP heaters ON
11:17:02											Start Run 5 @ 1000'
11:18:00	425			10							
11:20:00	650			10							
11:22:00	1100			20							
11:24:00	1050			30							
11:26:00	1100			40							
11:27:02											End of Run 5
11:29:30	1000		Overheat	30							Start Profile 5 from 1000'
11:30:19											End of Profile 5 @ 1500'
11:30:28											Start Run 6 @ 1500'
11:31:00	600			20							
11:33:00	900			1000							Cloud
11:35:00	620			20							
11:37:00	500			20							
11:39:00	650			15							
11:40:32											End of Run 6
11:40:35	650			15							Start Profile 6 from 1500'
11:42:00	860		ON	15							End of Profile 6 @ 2000'
11:44:07											Start Run 7 @ 2000'
11:45:00	270		64	15							
11:47:00	900			15							
11:49:00	330			15							
11:51:00	380		64	15							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:53:00	380		64	15							
11:54:10											End of Run 7
11:55:34	470			15							Start Profile 7 from 2000'
11:57:20	600			15							End of Profile 7 @ 1000'
12:01:00			Overheat								
12:02:37											Start Orbits @ 1000'
12:13:14											End of 4 th Orbit
12:22:45											Start Orbits
12:27:17											End of 6 th Orbit
12:31:04			ON								Start Run 8 @ 1000'
12:32:00	500		64	15							
12:34:00	530			15							
12:36:00	1300			20							
12:38:00	720			20							PCASP heaters OFF
12:40:00	650		65	15							
12:42:00	500			10							
12:44:00	430			10							PCASP heater ON
12:46:00	430			10							
12:48:00	470			10							
12:50:00	310			8							PCASP heaters OFF
12:52:00	350			10							
12:54:00	360		Overheat	10							
12:56:00	280			10							PCASP heater ON
12:58:00	200			10							
13:00:00	255			10							
13:02:00	300			10							PCASP heaters OFF
13:02:22			ON								End of Run 8 Start P 8 from 1000'
13:04:26	170		74	2							FL020
13:06:11	250			5							FL030
13:07:20	270			5							FL040
13:08:25	400			5							FL050
13:09:23	400			5							End of Profile 8 @ FL060

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 30/8/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:11:40											Start Run 9 @ FL060
13:12:00	350		74	5							
13:14:00	340			5							
13:16:00	200			5							PCASP heaters ON
13:18:00	440			5							
13:20:00	190			5							
13:22:00	90			5							PCASP heaters OFF
13:24:00	150			5							
13:26:00											
13:28:15											End of Run 9 Start P 9 @ FL060
13:29:37	250			5							FL050
13:30:27	400			10							End of P 9 @ FL040
13:30:40											Start Run 10 @ FL040
13:31:00	330			10							
13:33:00	320			10							
13:33:34											End of Run10 Start P10 from FL040
13:34:36	420			8							3000'
13:35:53	670		75	8							2000'
13:37:16	750			10							End of Profile 10 @ 1000'
13:38:48											Start Orbits
13:45:50											End of Orbits
13:48:02											Start Profile 11 from 1000'
13:48:56	260			10							2000'
13:49:50	400		Overheat	5							3000'
13:50:56											End of Profile 11 @ 4000'
13:53:00											Start Run 11 @ 4000'
13:55:00	400			10							
13:57:00	600			5							
15:59:00	220			5							
14:01:00	680			5							PCASP heaters ON
14:03:00	300			5							
14:05:00	450		ON	10							

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:07:00	380		75	10							
14:09:00	550			10							PCASP heaters OFF
14:11:24											End of Run
14:14:08	1600			10							Start Profile 12 from 100'
14:16:25	620			10							FL010
14:17:20	450			15							FL020
14:18:20	420			10							FL030
14:19:27	380			10							FL040
14:22:28	380			10							FL050
14:23:21	255			10							FL060
14:27:10	420			10							FL070
14:28:01	400			8							FL080
14:28:45	240			5							FL090
14:29:45	110			5							FL100
14:32:32	190			5							FL110
14:33:35	90			5							FL120
14:34:42	60			5							FL130
14:35:56	25			2							FL140
14:37:05	50		75	2							End of Profile 12 @ FL150
PCASP CH 4 to 15 Only SEADAS Tape 1 time offset = 0											

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	30/8/04	Flight	B 046
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	30 100215 Z		Arrival	30 145000Z	

Physical system setup

Module Number Serial	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check After system stabilizes

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 Secs	at time?	30 091000 Z
Freezer temp	-8°C			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 046** Date **30/8/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **1** of **3**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

09500Z						Video start.
09500Z						Dark current view.
095500Z			90°A	Auto		ND 3.0 Filters fitted to both NIR & Vis DATA record start.
100215						tube off
100740			0°			
101424	P1	050 → 400ft	0°	Auto		P1 Fl 050 → 400ft
101922	P1		46°F	Auto		into sun
102058	P1					end P1 - - - * LOW LEVEL HAZE, MIST HAS COATED
	P2	400ft → 2000ft				start P2 - - - * INSTRUMENT WINDOW.
102232	P2	2000ft				end P2 - - -
102517	R1	2000ft	31°A	Auto		Start R1 Down sun run
102930	R1	2000ft	28°A	Auto		Strongest signal position. IR
103000	R1	2000ft	30°A	Auto.		- " - " - Vis
103517	R1					END R1
103723	R2	2000ft	45°F	Auto		Start R2 into sun Run. 0.25 Sec Sample
104723	R2	2000ft	45°F	Auto.		END R2
104803	P3	2000 → 1500ft	45°F	Auto		P2 to 1500ft
104905	P3	1500ft		Auto		end P3
105101	R3	1500ft	29°A	Auto		Start R3 Down sun Run. 27°A NIR MAX ~ 46000. 28°A Vis MAX ~ 46000
110058	R3	1500ft	~ 28.5°A	Auto		END R3
110205	P4	1500ft → 1000ft	~ 28.5°A	Auto		Start P4
110348	P4	1000ft	~ 28.5°A	Auto		END P4
110540	R4	1000ft	~ 45°F	Auto		Start R4 into sun run
111702	R5	1000ft	~ 28.5°A	Auto		start R5 Down sun run
112701	R5	1000ft	~ 28.5°A	Auto		END R5.
112925	P5	1000ft → 1500ft	~ 45°F	Auto		start P5 1000ft → 1500ft
113019	P5					END P5 @ 1500ft
113028	R6	1500ft	~ 45°F	Auto		start R6. into sun run.
113250	R6	1500ft	~ 44°F			track sun @ approx 44°F.
114029	R6	1500ft	~ 44°F			End R6
114039	P6	1500ft → 2000ft				start P6
114159	P6	2000ft	~ 44°F	Auto		END P6
114407	R7	2000ft	~ 29°A	Auto		start R7. Down sun. zenith 37.5° Pitch 7.6°
115407	R7	2000ft		Auto		End R7.
115535	P7	2000ft	0°			Start P7 → 1000ft
115721	P7	1000ft	0°			End P7 @ 1000ft
120234	orbit 1	1000ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 1
120410	orbit 1	800ft	6°F	15	30	end orbit 1 ~ 40° Left wing down.
120520	orbit 2	1000ft	6°F	15	30	start orbit 2

ND3
P. filters
fitted

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 046** Date **30/8/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **2** of **2**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

} Filters
Fitter

120652	orbit 2	1000ft	6°F	15	30	end orbit 2
120827	--- 3	1000ft	6°F	15	30	start orbit 3
121003	--- 3	1000ft	6°F	15	30	end --- 3
121134	--- 4	1000ft	6°F	15	30	start --- 4
121314	--- 4					end --- 4
122100						Filters Removed
122245	orbit 5	1000ft	6°F	10	10	orbit 5 39.5° Left wing down
122409	"	1000ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit 5
122547	" 6	1000ft	6°F	10	10	start orbit 6
122711	"	1000ft	6°F	10	10	end orbit 6
123052	R8	1000ft	50°F	Auto		Scanning 10° every 1 minute.
123240		1000ft	40°F	Auto		
123335		1000ft	30°F	Auto		
123435		1000ft	20°F	Auto		
123535		1000ft	10°F	Auto		
123635		1000ft	0°	Auto		1.5 secs sample period.
123735		1000ft	10°A	Auto		
123835		1000ft	20°A	Auto		
123935		1000ft	30°A	Auto		
124035		1000ft	40°A	Auto		
124135		1000ft	50°A	Auto		
124235		1000ft	60°A	Auto		
124335		1000ft	50°A	Auto		
124435		1000ft	40°A	Auto		
124535		1000ft	30°A	Auto		
124635		1000ft	20°A	Auto		
124735		1000ft	10°A	Auto		
124835		1000ft	0°	Auto		
124935		1000ft	10°F	Auto		
125035		1000ft	20°F	Auto		
125135		1000ft	30°F	Auto		
125235		1000ft	40°F	Auto		
125335		1000ft	50°F	Auto		
125435						Scanning end.
125435		1000ft	0°	Auto		
130232	R8	1000ft				end R8
130232	P8	1000ft				start P8 → F1060
130618				Auto		Sample rate to 1 sec.
130920	P8	6000ft	0°	Auto		end P8 @ F1060
13	P9	F1060 - 4000ft	0°			start P9 → 4000ft
	P9	4000ft	0°	Auto		P9 end
133040	R10	4000ft	0°	Auto		sample rate 1.5 secs

} Filters
Removed

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B046	DATE: 30/08/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: Adriatic Sea, Italy		PROJECT: ADRIEX _ flight to investigate radiative impact of aerosols along Adriatic Sea.	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	N2	Argon/CO2	CO
PRE FLIGHT	psi / 130 bar	psi / 160 bar	psi / 50 bar
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)		
//04						-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: last calibration data from previous flight for comparison with today.													
4:40:00	Ground		87.19	61.32	5346.26	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: First cal of day. Cal @04:45Z													
04:51:00	ground		96.67	52.32	5057.48	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: Air sample pipe (ASP) closed. CO cal max values : HORACE not on to check this.													
07:09:00	ground	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed. NOx zero													
07:38:	ground	-	82.03	66.16	5427.09	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 452 & 0.4 Rubbish													
08:46:14	ground	-	77.06	69.86	5383.24	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Remarks: ASP closed.													
09:35:38	ground	75.47	71.43	5391.12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:	3.80	Press Monocr	0.75	Press Cell:	7.12	Press Cal Gas	2.60	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	28.18	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 513-522													
09:56:45	ground	taxiing	77.88	70.89	5591.98	177.203	44	0.48	4.41	4.90	7.99		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 565-548													
10:13:44	FL050	-	77.05	70.81	5455.65	119.616	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: ASP now open. CO cal max values : 510-515													
10:27:02	FL020	R1	78.21	70.21	5490.63	126.155	74	-0.01	1.34	1.33	4.99		
	Flow Lamp:	33.85	Press Monocr	0.77	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.59	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	27.55	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 530-535 Cal ran into R1as cleaning began.													
11:34:00	FL150	R6	82.85	63.38	5251.10	126.155	65	0.19	1.71	1.90	4.96		
	Flow Lamp:	33.87	Press Monocr	0.78	Press Cell:	7.12	Press Cal Gas	2.60	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.63	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 566-551 (bit high)													
11:46:05	FL020	Into R7	83.42	62.67	5227.97	142.782	61	-0.03	0.61	0.60	4.57		
	Flow Lamp:	33.04	Press Monocr	0.78	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.60	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.53	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 526-530													
12:00:52	FL010	-	83.81	62.26	5218.36	178.676	-	-	-	-	-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 527-531													
12:32:08	FL010	Into R8	84.10	61.21	5147.74	152.234	68	0.08	1.95	2.04	5.06		
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.78	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.61	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.33	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 524-530													
13:12:48	FL060	Into R9	84.04	60.36	5072.99	137.111	72	-0.12	0.90	0.78	4.69		
	Flow Lamp:	33.98	Press Monocr	0.76	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.60	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.28	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 532-524 (Cal started 13:09:20) Cal ran into R9 by approx. 40 secs.													
13:40:53	FL040	Into O7	84.30	59.91	5050.67	96.060	78	-0.05	1.46	1.42	4.48		
	Flow Lamp:	34.01	Press Monocr	0.77	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.61	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.25	PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values : 533-520													
::	FL										-		
	Flow Lamp:		Press Monocr		Press Cell:		Press Cal Gas		Lamp °C		Monocr °C		PMT °C
Remarks: CO cal max values :													
::													
	Remarks: CO cal max values :												

Flight Manager's Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B046

Instruments

PSAP - analogue opp does not equal instrument display or RS232 output. PSAP RS232 data being recorded on to Neph/PSAP/Filter rack P.C.

SWS - window covered in layer of dirt from polluted layer flown through early in flight

14045
HOTAS - update flight summary and flight summary pages - cannot be displayed due to "page cannot be displayed - cannot find server or DNS error" or update page has null data

- derived data windows - display null data. Cannot display graphs

- Reverted to old X window display

- closing down windows throughout a/c seemed to help bring back FM display

RFC - ~~was~~ over-exposed

Aircraft

1 u/s headset

Strong breakthrough from pilots intercom - when they are speaking to each other NOT via the intercom then - microphones still pick up

New plot, same times

Flight B046 12:54:43

Heading 142 deg Speed 209 knots Height 0.9kft Press 980mb

Lat 43.8N Long 13.8E Wind 3 ms-1/ 127 deg

Temp 22.63C Dewpoint 17.57C

From 10:01:59 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	46482	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
—	NEPH BLUE SP	196.48	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
—	NEPH GREEN SP	97.31	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
—	NEPH RED SP	58.71	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

New plot, same times

Flight B046 10:44:03

Heading 169 deg Speed 219 knots Height 1.9kft Press 945mb

Lat 44.8N Long 12.8E Wind 5 ms-1/ 271 deg

Temp 20.97C Dewpoint 10.81C

From 10:05:46 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

38643

secs

All

— LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX

77.44

W m-2

C

New plot, same times**Flight B046 11:10:30**

Heading 179 deg Speed 209 knots Height 0.9kft Press 979mb

Lat 44.9N Long 12.9E Wind 1 ms-1/ 283 deg

Temp 21.91C Dewpoint 15.46C

From 10:05:46 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

40230

secs

All

— LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX

67.83

 W m^{-2}

C

New plot, same times**Flight B046 11:10:13**

Heading 179 deg Speed 208 knots Height 0.9kft Press 979mb

Lat 45.0N Long 12.9E Wind 2 ms-1/ 302 deg

Temp 22.08C Dewpoint 15.85C

From 10:43:17 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

40212 secs

All

UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX

689.29

W m-2

C

New plot, same times**Flight B046 11:11:20**

Heading 179 deg Speed 210 knots Height 0.9kft Press 979mb

Lat 44.9N Long 12.9E Wind 2 ms-1/ 263 deg

Temp 21.88C Dewpoint 15.47C

From 10:50:36 to now

Current values

TIME FROM MIDNIGHT

40278

secs

All

— LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX

66.82

 $W m^{-2}$

C

New plot, same times

Flight B046 11:50:02

Heading 16 deg Speed 204 knots Height 1.9kft Press 945mb

Lat 44.9N Long 12.8E Wind 4 ms-1/ 259 deg

Temp 21.28C Dewpoint 10.41C

From 11:17:20 to now

Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	42600	secs
—	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	70.25	$W m^{-2}$

⌂ All
⌂

New plot, same times**Flight B046 11:50:21**

Heading 16 deg Speed 204 knots Height 1.8kft Press 945mb

Lat 45.0N Long 12.8E Wind 4 ms-1/ 257 deg

Temp 21.63C Dewpoint 10.51C

From 10:43:17 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 42621 secs All
 — UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX 795.73 $W\ m^{-2}$